

The Step- m Eulerian Triangle: Mirror Symmetry and Universal Growth Rate

Executive Summary for OEIS/Zenodo

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Definition. For a parameter $m \in \mathbb{C}$, the *step- m Eulerian triangle* $\{T^{(m)}(n, k) : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} T^{(m)}(1, 1) &= 1, & T^{(m)}(n, 1) &= T^{(m)}(n, n) = 1 \quad (n \geq 1), \\ T^{(m)}(n, k) &= (m(n - k) + 1)T^{(m)}(n - 1, k - 1) + (m(k - 1) + 1)T^{(m)}(n - 1, k). \end{aligned}$$

At $m = 1$, this reduces to the classical Eulerian numbers: $T^{(1)}(n, k) = A(n, k - 1)$.

Row polynomial and row sum. The *row polynomial* is $R_n^{(m)}(y) = \sum_{k=1}^n T^{(m)}(n, k) y^{k-1}$ (degree $n - 1$, constant term 1). The *row sum* satisfies $S_n(m) = R_n^{(m)}(1) = \prod_{j=0}^{n-2} (mj + 2)$.

Center variable. The entire theory is organized around the **center variable** $u := m + 1$.

Theorem 1 (Universal Growth Law and Mirror Invariance). *For $u = m + 1 \neq 0$, the Lyapunov exponent $\beta(m) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log |\alpha_{\max}(n, m)|$ satisfies*

$$\boxed{\beta(m) = \beta(-m - 2) = \log |u|}.$$

Proof methods. (1) *Column generating functions:* OGF has pole at $x = 1/u$, yielding $\beta = \log |u|$.
(2) *Transfer-product / Rouché:* Mirror invariance follows from $|(-m - 2) + 1| = |-u| = |u|$.

Conjecture 2 (Parity Positivity). *For integer $m \leq -3$, every even row n has entrywise nonnegative coefficients.*

Verification. For $m \in \{-3, -4, -5\}$, all even rows $n \leq 400$ are entrywise nonnegative.

OEIS correspondences.

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m	$ u $	Description	Limit const.	OEIS
0	1	Pascal's triangle	—	A007318
1	2	Classical Eulerian numbers	1	A008292
-1	0	Degenerate ($\beta = -\infty$)	—	A144431
-2	1	MTSR critical point	—	A225372
-3	2	Mirror of $m = 1$; has complex roots	1/3	A392664
-4	3	Mirror of $m = 2$; all real roots	1/6	A392665
-5	4	Mirror of $m = 3$; all real roots	1/10	A392666

Scaled root domain. Setting $z = y/|u|^n$, the scaled zeros concentrate in a fixed annulus. Green: EK bounds; red dashed: actual $\max|z|$.

Figure 1: $m = 1 \leftrightarrow m = -3$ ($|u| = 2$). Note: $m = -3$ has **complex roots**.

Figure 2: $m = 2 \leftrightarrow m = -4$ ($|u| = 3$). EK bounds very tight (99.9%, 96.8%).

Figure 3: $m = 3 \leftrightarrow m = -5$ ($|u| = 4$). Both have **all real roots**; limit $\rightarrow 1/10$.

Distinguishing features of the new sequences.

Property	$m = -3$	$m = -4$	$m = -5$
$ u $	2	3	4
$\beta = \log u $	0.693	1.099	1.386
Mirror partner	$m = 1$ (Eulerian)	$m = 2$	$m = 3$
Limit constant	$1/3 \approx 0.333$	$1/6 \approx 0.167$	$1/10 = 0.100$
Even-row roots	Complex pairs	All real	All real
EK tightness (n=12)	57.8%	96.8%	99.9%

Data and code. Archived at Zenodo: doi:10.5281/zenodo.18446568.

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